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DESIGNNOVATION STUDIO

NEW EDUCATIONAL PLATFORM FOR DESIGN AS CONNECTING

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ABSTRACT

Design has been evolving from Doing to Thinking and will eventually be evolved to Connecting. This change is so radical and thus it is highly crucial to educate students ready for the changes to come.

Designnovation Studio has created as an open and adaptable design studio to provide students with the experience of horizontal and vertical connection.

Students from any discipline (design and non-design) and level (undergraduate and graduate) may participate in projects. Depending on their level, interest, and experiences, each student plays different role in their teams, such as, designer, design manager, researcher, facilitator, and documenter. This helps students getting better idea about their future career.

The paper describes the significance, structure, advantage, and successful outputs of Designnovation Studio as a model for new educational platform. Also, common obstacles and potentials are discussed for those who are planning to create similar design studio courses.

Keywords: Designnovation Studio, Design Innovation, Connecting

INTRODUCTION: DESIGN IS CHANGING AND SO SHALL BE THE DESIGNERS.

The profession of industrial design has been remarkably evolved despite its relatively short history. Its nature, purpose, scope, required skillset have been changing. Figure 1 summarizes the evolution of design from yesterday, today and tomorrow.

In the past, design was concerned about creating things that are beautiful and useful so that industry

can produce and sell more. Designer's role was limited to visualizing the concept and making the concept into product. In most cases, design dealt with engineering constraints. In the school, students learn how to visualize and how to make. The rationale for the new design usually comes from marketing and product planning group and designers play a role where professional knowledge and skill

Today, design is concerned about creating new and better experience for the users. Design is now more driven by the users and market rather than engineering. In order to create things that can offer better experience, designers need to learn what users would need and want. Designer's role has expanded and thinking became an important component in design process. In schools, students would learn conducting design research as well as drawing and making.

Tomorrow - which already began - design will be more concerned about creating value. Design will be driven by value for the users, industry, community, and eventually the earth. In order to create more value, designers should be able to learn how to make meaningful connections. Connecting resources, stakeholders, and various insights will be the core of profession of design. In schools, students should learn how to see the challenges and turn that into opportunities by connecting dots. This cannot be taught in typical design studios.

In this new paradigm, designers are required to understand and communicate with other parties involved in design development. Designers are already able to choose from variety roles to play, such as designer, researcher, strategist, and facilitator. In a nutshell, designers should be aware of the changes to come and the fact that the change is already happening.

Figure 1. The evolution of design procession and education

In order to educate designers to cope with the changing roles, there is a need for new platform of design education that is more open, flexible, and encouraging students to play different roles so that it can lead students to learn to participate in innovation by design. More importantly, an environment where designers can learn to communicate with non-designers is necessary in the new paradigm of design as connecting.

PROBLEMS OF TYPICAL DESIGN STUDIO EDUCATION

In typical design education, students (designers) interact with faculty (designer) and other students (designers). Also, students are in same level with the rest of the class, and they all play same roles - designer. This environment cannot offer enough diversity in specialty and variety of insights and perspectives.

This format of studios actually works well for beginner students, such as, sophomores, when knowledge and skill for design are taught mainly. For upper class students, however, learning how to communicate and collaborate with other discipline is crucial for the success in future career.

Another typical drawback of studio education is that the faculty or instructor gives the topic, the process, methods, and the schedule in most cases. Students, thus, cannot learn how to strategize and pursue their own project by themselves efficiently.

Interdisciplinary collaborative studios are to provide students with valuable experiences, in which students from various fields - design and non-design students to work on a shared project. This is ideal for the projects that are systematic and complicated in nature. Students will learn the importance of communication beyond their own disciplines.

Often corporations sponsor collaborative studios, and students get opportunity of getting some glimpse of the 'real-world' experience. This has two sides - benefits and drawbacks. The benefits are that the students can learn from the handling the practical design constraints and the feedback and mentorship from the sponsor. The drawbacks are the potential of lack of academic pedagogy if the sponsor is too inclined to get the outcome. Obviously keeping the balance is the key for the success.

CONNECTOR: FUTURE PORTRAIT OF DESIGNERS

Defining the role of design helps figuring out the new format of design studio education. In the past, designers typically work as line workers - receive input from planning, develop designs, and deliver the outcome to engineering. In this flow, designers work as designers. (Figure 2. Left)

Today, design is playing crucial role in collaborative environments creating valuable connections among concepts, constraints, and solutions from various resources. Thus there is a need for a new portrait of designer - the connector. (Figure 2. Right)

Figure 2. Design in a linear process and Design as a connecting.

Connector understands, communicates, discovers, and synthesizes to create more meaningful outputs. To become a successful designer as a connector, one needs to have characteristics suitable for and experiences in understanding, communicating, and working with people in different fields.

Also, students should be given with opportunities to experience different roles, such as designer, manager, planner, researcher, and communicator. This helps working in a system in various roles by gaining fluency in professional languages and flexibility in thinking.

DESIGNNOVATION STUDIO

The Designnovation Studio has created to educate students to be more effective connectors and to create innovation by design. In order to achieve the goals, the studio needed to have several unique aspects as described below.

DESIGN STUDIO OUTSIDE OF DESIGN STUDIO

In order to make Designnovation Studio function as a “design studio outside of design studio,” the studio was away from other regular design studios. One of the advantages from being geographically outside of design studio is that the students from other majors feel less ‘alien.’ This is same to design major students as they feel they are in more ‘neutral

zone’, which makes them to see bigger pictures of the projects.

DESIGN THE PROCESS. THEN DESIGN THE PRODUCT

The faculty advisors give a design brief, expected deliverables, and anticipated milestones. Then each team decides detailed tactics and action items. This encourages students to design the process from their perspective, not the viewpoint from the professors, and allows students to get positive attitude rather than following schedule given by the professor.

Also, students learn how to formulate processes and methods to achieve certain outcomes. Teams would debate on what method will work better than others and how to lay a plan in research and development. In fact, discussing about the process than just the design helps students a lot by giving them chances to see the big picture.

TEAM STRUCTURES

Designnovation Studio is often called a “vertical-and-horizontal studio”; meaning participating students are from diverse majors - design and non-design, and diverse levels - graduate and undergraduate, including freshman - pretty similar to the ‘real world’ environment. This allows students play any roles they feel comfortable and they learn from various sources - faculty, upper classmen, lower classmen, and students from different fields. The

Figure 3. Comparison of three studio formats.

figure 3 shows this structure very well. The benefit from interdisciplinary design studio is that there are people with different background and specialty. The benefit from the Designnovation Studio is that people are from different experience level besides the background and specialty. It is more well mixed group of people, and each team has truly multi-faceted characters.

PLAY A ROLE. AND UNDERSTAND OTHER ROLES.

- Experiencing new way of designing

At Designnovation Studio, students are expected to perform a role from his/her main areas of study. For instance, industrial designers are to develop forms and structures of devices where digital design students are responsible for developing user interface designs. Not only the outcomes, but also the processes are different. Industrial design students tend to make sketches and physical study models as ideation process while digital students mostly work on computers making lo-fi prototypes and flash digital graphics.

In order to achieve higher level of innovation and to give opportunity unfamiliar learning experiences, students are encouraged work together on each phase. For example, students, despite their specialty, work on sketching and modeling. Students are exposed to new way of thinking and doing this way and much more innovative solutions are achieved.

- Experiencing and enhancing own specialty

In the beginning of the studio project, a faculty advisor would request each team to assign roles to team members for specific capacity or needs, such as the leader (or facilitator or manager), documenter, researcher(s), designer(s), and presenter(s).

As students spend time together on a same topic area, each student begins to realize his/her special interest, such as researching, designing, managing, documenting, and presenting. Then they can make more contribution with bigger motivation.

Also, since students are working in groups, they need

	week 1	week 2	week 3	week 4	week 5	week 6	week 7	week 8	week 9	week 10
phases	discovery Discover the consumer, context, and the contents.		define Define the design innovation gap.		develop Develop the designs of hardware and UI.			delivery Communication of design results.		
action items	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Team building - Brainstorm for inspirations - Kick-off - User & context survey - Preliminary review 		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Create avatars of the target user group - Investigate potential user experiences and define the innovation gap. 		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Midterm review - Initial designs of hardware, UI, and service - Make Lo-Fi prototypes of hardware and UI 		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Revise user experience scenario - Revise designs using user feedback 		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Final preview - Animation: ID, UI, Network - Prepare for the final presentation - Final presentation 	
deliverables	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Team themes - User/context research report - Current and ideal UX scenario 		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Definitions of users and their avatars, lifestyles, desires, innovation opportunities 		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Lo-Fi prototypes of hardware and UI - Pictures of Lo-Fi prototypes - User trials results 		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Storyboard and/or diagram showing user experience. - Finalized designs: ID, UI, and service - Animation of ID and UI 		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - UX and context - 3D model, and animations - Flash movies of UI - Team Process Books & presentations 	

Figure 4. Basic process of Designnovation Studio

to convince other members in the group. The documenter needs to collect information from the meetings and reviews and supply the information to the presenter. The presenter would put together for visual and verbal presentation and needs to get consent before making the presentation public.

This exercise teaches students a huge lesson of responsibility and team spirit. Of course, students realize the importance and challenge in effective communication.

DESIGN PROCESS AT DESIGNNOVATION STUDIO

The basic process format is Discovery - Defining - Develop - Delivery, Which is a classic design process. Each team of students is requested to develop their own strategy and tactics based on the process. From this, they are expected to learn how to create project framework.

DISCOVERY: Making the unfamiliar familiar and the familiar unfamiliar

Team building and immersing into the project topic are the main purpose of the phase. The topics, as well as the team members, are new. This is excellent as one can discover more when everything is unfamiliar.

If the topic is familiar to the students, reverse the situation and make the familiar unfamiliar. This is possible by interviewing with less related questions, such as *'what do you do when you spill coffee on the table?'* for the project to design printers. Another way is letting students begin the "journey" from far upstream, such as *'communication'* when designing future mobile phone. This is not achievable in normal design studios. Students work on their own project and expected to do all aspect of process and there is not much room for the student put more stress on a certain part of the project.

DEFINE: Understand the problem and find the innovative opportunities

Once the problem is defined through surveys and literature research, the teams define the innovative opportunities, which later convert into design concepts. Instead of fixing current problems, students are encouraged apply creative inspirations found from less related fields. For example, instead

of finding the way to design printers for corporate market, which is already saturated, students would find opportunities from areas where printers are not existing, for example, park and restaurants.

- DEVELOP: Formulate the solutions

With the innovation opportunities gathered, students write stories of desired user experience. The story then becomes the source for design development. Students, regardless of their specialty, create ideas for physical and digital design, business plan, and other areas of the system. For instance, not only industrial design students, but also others join the sketching. Obviously, the quality won't be as good as what the students in the specialty can produce. But to everyone's surprise, brilliant concepts are produced from this rather unusual experience. In later part of the development process, students with specific specialty will carry out the final designs to maintain the quality. Still, students will collaborate to make product and service work as a whole.

- DELIVERY: Validate and present the solutions

Validation is a necessary step in order to make the design innovation more meaningful. The designs will be demonstrated to the users they interviewed to get feedback for further refinement. Students will also work on creating the best way to present the new concept and design to the corporate sponsor. Comprehensive and compelling stories tells the new user experience and the designs will be presented as enablers of the experience.

CHALLENGES AND OPPORTUNITIES

The benefit of the Designnovation Studio was very clear. As one student put, *"The Designnovation Studio offers an incredible opportunity to collaborate across disciplines to work as a team in a manner that promotes inspired problem solving. In no other class have I experienced near the same level of cooperation, thoughtful methodology, and team building. The class really helped to improve my understanding of and approach to design research, my ability to communicate both informally within a group and formally through presentations, and altogether taught me an entirely new way to go about the design process. I would recommend it to*

anyone, but especially believe individuals outside of digital and industrial design - outside DAAP altogether - could bring an entirely new level of excellence to the experience. (Bridget Nicole)

But there are challenges as well, such as:

- Challenges for the faculty advisors

The first step is getting diverse students from various fields. This is doable in universities, but there are challenges, such as class schedule and interest from departments, which are not used to such studio courses.

The second challenge is maintaining the schedule. Since the teams are totally diverse, they need much more time to reduce the gaps and to get better consensus. In fact, this is the biggest benefit students get - learning how to work with others.

- Challenges for the students

The second challenge for the faculty advisors is the difficult task for the students, too.

Working with teammates who never worked with, speaking different professional ‘language’, and have totally different background and goals is very

challenging and students spend extensive time to get a team spirit.

However, students enjoy working in this team dynamics at the same time. They realize this is the main benefit from participating in the diverse teams.

- Opportunities for design education

Designnovation Studio expanded the horizon of design education by letting students learn more than how to design. Younger students can learn what they need to learn in coming years and older students can learn how to manage design projects. Design students can learn how to work efficiently with non-design students and vice versa.

- Opportunities for corporate sponsors

Corporations sponsoring Designnovation Studio discover innovative opportunities that exceed designs created from sponsored projects in traditional studios. According to the corporate sponsors, the outcomes are ‘multi-dimensional’, which never been expected in neither typical studios in schools or corporations.

Figure 5. Scenes from Designnovation Studio